

**A STUDY ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION TOWARDS SMARTPHONE AMONG
COLLEGE STUDENTS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO CUDDALORE
DISTRICT**

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ABSTRACT

Smartphone usage has proliferated in recent years. A Smart phone integrates a feature phone and a mobile computing platform, and recent model mobiles has several features like GPS navigation, Wi-Fi, digital cameras, media players and other applications. Due to Smartphone convenience these days people give the impression to become reliant towards Smartphone. The youth today, especially the students, are technologically oriented and are into the usage of digital technology. College students consider the mobile phone as the technology of choice over laptops. The youth are the liveliest market in the adoption of digital technology and its newest applications and features. The youth segment is a segment of important concern to marketers. This is because the youth segments are fast adopters as well as innovative features and technology oriented. In the past decade, the mobile phone industry has more and more renowned the meaning of customer satisfaction and experience. In rapidly changing a critical factor for mobile phone industry is to maintain and improve their profitability. Satisfaction of the customer is an important advantage for the contemporary organizations and it helps in building long term relations as well as brand equity. Customer satisfaction is the cherished outcome of excellent business practice. In this article the researcher analyse the Smartphone user purchase behavior and their satisfaction.

KEYWORDS: consumer, buying behavior, smart phones, satisfaction,

I - INTRODUCTION

The mounting rivalry by mobile phone industry has led to augmented anxiety regarding which mobile phone device is valuable to own as a consumer bearing in mind the vast number of mobile phone brands and versions available to the market. This anxiety warrants the need to consider factors that presently determine consumers' choices of mobile phones taking into account the drenched level of the mobile phone trade. A mobile phone can be defined as a wireless device programmed with the main ability to make phone calls and receive text messages, among other functions. The mobile phones produced today are more portable and capable of carrying out several functions compared to the initial mobile phones. Mobile phones have various features that include games, music, camera, Global Positioning System (GPS), voice-active dialing, editing filters, video player and Microsoft Office functions (Agar, 2013). There are standard mobile phones and smartphones. The standard mobile phones perform basic functions of calling, sending text messages, telling time, alarm clock and calendar. A mobile device programmed with an advanced operating system is known as a smartphone (Parui, 2015). Typically, Smartphone's also comprise web browsers and high-resolution touch screens, which provide people better viewing and browsing experience. Consumers are capable of download and install different application in their operating systems. Commonly a Smartphone has operating systems that permit phone users to install different applications on it upon their wish. Most Smartphone's have high-speed mobile broadband 4G LTE internet, motion sensors, and mobile payment mechanisms. There are several reasons leading to the consumer's selection of purchase. Consumers respond to different stimuli, which in turn leads the consumers to react the way they do towards products and services" (Kotler et al., 2010: 147). Customer satisfaction is normally understood to be an important determinant of repeat sales, positive word-of-mouth, and customer loyalty. Customer satisfaction or dissatisfaction is determined by the overall thoughts, or feelings, a person has about a product after it has been purchased (Solomon, 2004).

II - REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Ling et al. (2006) conducted a study on diversified users' satisfaction with advanced mobile phone features on American college students. The respondents suggested improvement on camera, high voice recognition, and ease in the dialing function. Savitha Nair, Nivea Nelson

and Karthika (2016) in their study found that quality of the product is the most important factor influencing the choice, followed by mobile phone features. Genuine need triggers the want to purchase mobile phones. Touch screen and design and style are the most preferred aspects of the mobile phones. The findings of the study give insights to the players in the market in modification of their product, pricing and promotional strategies and so on. Riyath and Musthafa (2014) study on Sri Lankan university students showed that the most influential factor of mobile phone brand choice was price. Price had the highest mean score of 4.09 among nine variables tested. Middle and lower income earners expect price reduction as technology advances over time and new mobile phones are introduced. Kaushal and Rakesh (2016) studied to find out occurrence of any noteworthy variation between factors like Compatibility, Product Features, Price, Brand, relative advantage, dependency, social influence and convenience which affect consumer's purchase of Smartphone. The study exposed that only Compatibility, Dependency and Social pressure had a important effect on purchase goal of Smartphone users. Only convenience factor showed a important difference between male and female purchase goal. Karjaluo et al (2005) studied factors affecting consumer choice for mobile phones in Finland and found that price, brand and size of the phone are the main factors in purchase of any new mobile phone. Ling et al (2006) surveyed College students to identify their preference for the mobile phones. The result showed that material look, size and menu of the mobile phone are the most determinant factors affecting the buying behavior of consumers. According to Ibrahim, Kassim, and Mohamood (2013) found Promotion mix included celebrity endorsement, marketing frequency and exchange offers as the determining factors for purchase of Smart phone. It also established that societal pressure works more on adolescent customers while purchasing smart phones. Customers gather information regarding product from various sources, co-workers, friends, family etc earlier than making a product purchase. Dziwornu (2013) conducted a research on “factors affecting mobile phone purchase in the greater Accra region of Ghana”. Most of the respondents surveyed were used Nokia and Samsung mobile phones. The mobile phone users suggested that modern phones sold should have technological features that are durable and high quality. In addition, batteries produced should last longer.

OBJECTIVES

1. To study consumer choice in the selection of mobile phones
2. To estimate the customer satisfaction on various brands of Smartphone

3. To find out the factors influencing during purchase of Smartphone
4. To find out the features do students consider when making a purchase of a Smartphone

Scope of the study

In this study the researcher identified how smart phones influences the students day today life and why students use smart phone, and also identified the brand which is the more popular among the students. The researcher conducted the study during December 2019, and the data were collected from the under graduate arts and science students from Cuddalore districts of Tamilnadu, India and the number of sample limited to 100. Since the sample size is small, the result of this study cannot be generalized.

Limitations of the Study

The result obtained from this study is valid up to a certain extent only. Though there are different segments in Smartphone users, the researcher has selected only under graduate college students studying in arts and science stream. However, the findings of the present study may not be generalized to other segment of the users. Moreover, the data have been collected from the under graduate college students studying in arts and science stream in Cuddalore districts of Tamilnadu, India only.

III - RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The survey questionnaire included thirty three questions; all the questions have been used for this study. The purpose of using Smartphone was measured with Rank scale from one to eleven and type of social media most preferred by the respondents were measured with Rank scale from one to ten.

Collection of Primary Data

For the purpose of the present study, the necessary Primary data have been collected using a survey method with the help of a structured questionnaire administered in person from the respondents regarding their opinion about their Smartphone buying and usage behavior. The respondents of this study were arts and science students studying in Government and private colleges in cuddalore district of Tamilnadu, Indai. The researcher personally met the

respondents, and data collection has been done only after establishing personal rapport with the respondents. The researcher has totally collected 100 responses for the present study. Hence, the sample of 100 is considered for this study and a total of 100 responses were obtained during December 2019.

Collection of Secondary Data

The researcher collected secondary data on Smartphone sales trends, consumer satisfaction, various factors influencing in the purchase action. This information has been collected from Journals, Magazines, Reports and company's News Bulletin and Internet sources.

Statistical Tools Used

First hand information is collected from 100 respondents. Responses were coded and data entered and then analysed using a computer programme called Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) 20.0 to get inferences. Descriptive analysis were used to describe the sample, to show the numbers and percentage of items into categories, percentage analysis, Pearson Chi-Square test, and ranking method were used for this study.

IV - DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATIONS

Table – 1 Profile of the Respondents

Factors		Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percent
Gender	Male	37	37.0	37.0
	Female	63	63.0	100.0
Type of Family	Nuclear Family	12	12.0	12.0
	Joint Family	88	88.0	100.0
Marital Status	Married	14	14.0	14.0
	Unmarried	86	86.0	100.0

Source: Primary Data

Totally 100 respondents were considered for this study. Among the respondents 37% of the respondents were male and 63% of respondents were female. Regarding the type of family 12% of the respondents belongs to nuclear family and rest of the 88% of the respondents

belongs to joint family. And from the data it is identified that 14% of the respondents were married respondents and 86% of them were unmarried. From the data it is found that most of the respondents were female and most of the respondents come from joint family and unmarried.

Table – 2 Factors Influenced to buy a Smart phone among Gender

Crosstabulation									
			Factors Influenced					Total	
			Price	Offers	Features	Advertisement	Performance		
GENDE R	Male	Count	15	6	21	6	12	37	
		% within GENDE R	40.5 %	16.2 %	56.8 %	16.2 %	32.4 %		
		Femal e	Count	23	12	16	1	14	63
		% within GENDE R	36.5 %	19.0 %	25.4 %	1.6% %	22.2 %		
	Total		Count	38	18	37	7	26	100
	Percentages and totals are based on respondents.								
a. Dichotomy group tabulated at value 1.									

Source: Primary Data

Table 2 shows the factors influenced to buy a Smartphone, among the respondents 40.5% of the male and 36.5% of the female respondents gives priority to price of the Smartphone and 56.8% of male respondents and 25.4% of the female respondents are given importance to features of the Smartphone and followed by performance of the Smartphone male (32.4%) and female (22.2%), offers given for the Smartphone male (16.2%) and female (19.0%) and they respondents given least importance to advertisement male respondents (16.2%) and female respondents (1.6%). From the study it is concluded that the respondents given more importance to Features of the Smartphone and price. Respondents were given least importance to advertisement of the product.

Table – 3 Brand preference of the Respondents

			Factors Influenced					Total	
			Price	Offers	Features	Advertisement	Performance		
BRAND	Apple	Count	2	0	1	0	0	3	
		% within BRAND	66.7%	0.0%	33.3%	0.0%	0.0%		
	Samsung	Count	6	4	8	0	8	25	
		% within BRAND	24.0%	16.0%	32.0%	0.0%	32.0%		
	Sony	Count	3	2	4	0	2	5	
		% within BRAND	60.0%	40.0%	80.0%	0.0%	40.0%		
	Honor	Count	2	0	1	0	3	6	
		% within BRAND	33.3%	0.0%	16.7%	0.0%	50.0%		
	Oppo	Count	1	0	1	0	0	2	
		% within BRAND	50.0%	0.0%	50.0%	0.0%	0.0%		
	Vivo	Count	5	4	5	4	6	13	
		% within BRAND	38.5%	30.8%	38.5%	30.8%	46.2%		
		Mi/Redmi	Count	5	4	5	4	6	46
			% within BRAND	52.5%	40.8%	78.5%	64.8%	38.0%	
Total		Count	19	10	20	4	19	100	
Percentages and totals are based on respondents.									
a. Dichotomy group tabulated at value 1.									

Source: Primary Data

Table – 3 shows the respondents level of influencing factor to buy specific brands of Smartphone. Among the respondents, 46% prefer to buy Mi/Redmi brand of Smartphone and the influencing factors are new features in Smartphone (78.5%), advertisement for the product (64.8%), Price of the Smartphone (52.5%) offers (40.8%) and performance (38.0%).

Samsung Smartphone is preferred by 25% of the respondents and the influencing factors are features and performance in Smartphone (32%), price of the Smartphone (24%) and product offers (16.0%). Other preferred brands are Vivo (13%), Honor (6%), Sony (5%), Apple (3%) and Oppo (2%). From the analysis it is found that most preferred brand of Smartphone is Mi/Redmi (46%) and influencing factor to buy a mobile phone is new feature in Smartphone, advertisement and price. And Samsung Smartphone is second preferred brand (25%) and influencing factors are new features in Smartphone, performance and price finally the least preferred brand is Oppo with (2%) and influencing factors are price and features of the Smartphone.

Table – 4 Satisfaction level of Response among Gender

Group Statistics						
	GENDER	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-value	sig
SATISFIED	Male	37	4.59	.599	5.252	.000
	Female	63	3.27	1.461		

Source: Primary Data

Table – 4 shows the satisfaction level of response between male and female respondents. To know the satisfaction level among the male and female respondents T- test was carried out, the result shows that there is a significant difference on satisfaction level among the respondents; Male respondents have more satisfaction (Mean value 4.59) than female respondents.

Table – 5 Satisfaction level of Respondents with Brand

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	F-Value	p-Value
Apple	3	4.33	.577	3.322	.005
Samsung	25	4.64	.569		
Sony	5	4.60	.548		
Honor	6	4.17	1.169		
Oppo	2	2.50	.707		
Vivo	13	4.54	.660		
Mi/Redmi	46	3.72	1.377		
Total	100	4.12	1.148		

Source: Primary Data

Table – 5 shows the satisfaction level of respondents among various brands of Smartphone. To know the satisfaction level of respondents among various brands one way ANOVA was carried out. The result shows that there is a significant difference on respondent's satisfaction level (.005). Samsung Smartphone users have more satisfaction than other brands because the mean value shows 4.64 than other brands of Smartphone. The study results shows that Samsung Smartphone user have more satisfaction than other brand users.

Table – 6 Satisfaction level of Respondents with Product Features

	GENDER	N	Mean	SD	t-value	Sig
Size & Display	Male	37	4.49	.651	102	.029
	Female	63	3.25	.421		
Processor	Male	37	4.24	1.116	104.25	.010
	Female	63	3.64	.775		
Battery Life	Male	37	4.38	.953	98	.620
	Female	63	4.25	1.332		
Internal Memory & Space	Male	37	4.41	.686	103.2	.024
	Female	63	3.86	.913		
Operating System	Male	37	4.46	.900	69.078	.099
	Female	63	4.16	.807		
Design and Function	Male	37	4.22	1.158	53.431	.730
	Female	63	4.14	.737		
Size	Male	37	4.19	1.050	55.853	.314
	Female	62	4.39	.710		
Camera	Male	37	4.62	.721	108.36	.018
	Female	63	3.89	.688		
Price	Male	37	4.05	1.153	98	.069
	Female	63	4.41	.796		

Source: Primary Data

Table – 6 shows the satisfaction level of respondents with product features. To know the satisfaction level among male and female respondents with respect to product features, t-test was carried out. The test results show that there is a significant difference among the male and female respondents with product features. Among the respondents male respondents have

more satisfaction with product features such as size and display, processor, internal memory and camera performance. From the study it is concluded that male respondents have more satisfaction than female respondents with the product features in size and display, processor, internal memory and camera performance.

Table – 7 Satisfaction level of Respondents with Product Features and Brands

					ANOVA Result	
Factors	Brand Name	N	Mean	SD	F-Value	p-value
Size & Display	Apple	3	5.00	.000	1.101	.368
	Samsung	25	4.20	.577		
	Sony	5	4.60	.548		
	Honor	6	4.17	.753		
	Oppo	2	4.00	.000		
	Vivo	13	4.31	.630		
	Mi/Redmi	46	4.39	.682		
	Total	100	4.34	.639		
Processor	Apple	3	5.00	.000	3.678	.003
	Samsung	25	4.08	.812		
	Sony	5	4.60	.548		
	Honor	6	3.00	1.673		
	Oppo	2	3.00	.000		
	Vivo	13	4.62	.650		
	Mi/Redmi	46	4.35	.924		
	Total	100	4.24	.965		
Battery Life	Apple	3	5.00	.000	.926	.480
	Samsung	25	4.56	.712		
	Sony	5	4.60	.548		
	Honor	6	4.67	.516		
	Oppo	2	4.50	.707		
	Vivo	13	4.31	1.109		

	Mi/Redmi	46	4.02	1.527		
	Total	100	4.30	1.202		
Internal Memory & Space	Apple	3	5.00	.000	.528	.786
	Samsung	25	4.40	.764		
	Sony	5	4.80	.447		
	Honor	6	4.50	.548		
	Oppo	2	4.50	.707		
	Vivo	13	4.62	.650		
	Mi/Redmi	46	4.33	1.117		
	Total	100	4.44	.903		
Operating System	Apple	3	5.00	.000	2.444	.031
	Samsung	25	4.28	.542		
	Sony	5	4.80	.447		
	Honor	6	4.67	.516		
	Oppo	2	4.00	1.414		
	Vivo	13	4.69	1.109		
	Mi/Redmi	46	4.00	.894		
	Total	100	4.27	.851		
Design and Function	Apple	3	5.00	.000	2.444	.031
	Samsung	25	4.52	.510		
	Sony	5	4.40	.548		
	Honor	6	3.33	1.862		
	Oppo	2	3.50	.707		
	Vivo	13	4.00	1.000		
	Mi/Redmi	46	4.09	.865		
	Total	100	4.17	.911		
Size	Apple	3	5.00	.000	2.257	.045
	Samsung	25	4.38	.576		
	Sony	5	4.60	.548		
	Honor	6	3.33	1.862		
	Oppo	2	3.50	.707		
	Vivo	13	4.31	.630		

	Mi/Redmi	46	4.37	.826		
	Total	100	4.31	.853		
Camera	Apple	3	5.00	.000	.426	.860
	Samsung	25	4.56	.651		
	Sony	5	4.60	.894		
	Honor	6	4.33	.516		
	Oppo	2	4.50	.707		
	Vivo	13	4.69	.480		
	Mi/Redmi	46	4.59	.686		
	Total	100	4.59	.637		
Price	Apple	3	5.00	.000	.612	.720
	Samsung	25	4.16	.987		
	Sony	5	4.40	.894		
	Honor	6	4.50	.548		
	Oppo	2	5.00	.000		
	Vivo	13	4.23	1.481		
	Mi/Redmi	46	4.24	.848		
	Total	100	4.28	.954		

Source: Primary Data

Table – 7 explains the respondent opinion towards satisfaction level of product features with different brands. The data are grouped according to the brand features. Mean value and standard deviation value are calculated for each features. From the mean score, most of the respondents have given more importance towards the processor, operating system, design and function, and size while selecting the mobile phone. But, in case of size and display, battery life, internal memory, camera and price of mobile are factors considered as a least important factor.

Ho: There is no significant difference of opinion towards purchase of mobile phone based on the product features.

In order to examine the stated hypothesis, one way ANOVA is applied. From the test value, it is noted that the mobile phone processor, operating system, design and function, size are significantly differs, other factors are not varied based on the product features. Hence, the stated Null hypothesis (Ho) is rejected.

V - FINDINGS

- It is identified that 14% of the respondents were married respondents and 86% of them were unmarried. From the data it is found that most of the respondents were female and most of the respondents come from joint family and unmarried
- It is concluded that the respondents given more importance to Features of the Smartphone and price. Respondents were given less importance to advertisement of the product.
- From the analysis it is found that most preferred brand of Smartphone is Mi/Redmi (46%) and influencing factor to buy a mobile phone is new feature in Smartphone, advertisement and price. And Samsung Smartphone is second preferred brand (25%) and influencing factors are new features in Smartphone, performance and price finally the least preferred brand is Oppo with (2%) and influencing factors are price and features of the Smartphone.
- To know the satisfaction level among the male and female respondents T- test was carried out, the result shows that there is a significant difference on satisfaction level among the respondents; Male respondents have more satisfaction (Mean value 4.59) than female respondents.
- The study results shows that overall satisfaction level of respondents, among various brands, Samsung Smartphone user have more satisfaction level than other brand users.
- The study results show that there is a significant difference among the male and female respondents with product features. It is concluded that male respondents have more satisfaction than female respondents with the product features such as size and display, processor, internal memory and camera performance.

VI - CONCLUSION

This study is about the satisfaction on smart phone among college students. In this study, students buying a variety of smart phones which satisfy his/her want and they are always

influenced by various factors. From this study we can understand consumer buying behavior towards smart phones.

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